

The Cultural Dimension of Image Readability

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Abstract

This article focuses on the role that cultural bias plays in lowering the readability of an instructional illustration. Taking theoretical frameworks by Lantz (1996) and Mody (1991) as a point of departure, the various approaches that the producer of an illustration can follow in order to reduce culturally based readability barriers are explored. These include: (a) avoiding deliberate prejudice and unintended neglect on both the literal and figurative levels of meaning, as well as; (b) ensuring adequate audience participation during the design phase of the instructional illustration.

Introduction

Cultural bias has often been described as a key reason why an instructional illustration is only partially comprehended or entirely misunderstood, especially when the producer and the recipient of the illustration do not share the same cultural background. From the point of view of the producer, the reduction of culturally based readability barriers may at first seem an impossible obstacle to overcome when one considers that the dominant outlook or world view in a specific target community is shaped by many different factors that include levels of literacy and formal education, political and religious indoctrination, superstitions, as well as the desire to preserve established traditions (Wagner, 1993:11). However, two main perspectives may prove helpful when dealing with the issue. These concern: (a) image processing phases suggested by Lantz (1996), and; (b) an audience-participation based approach described by Mody (1991).

Image readability

Image readability broadly refers to the ease with which the preferred

target group (Pettersson, 1984, 1993:159). The term originally stems from education research concerned with the selection of reading material for children of different age groups (Sevrin & Tankard, 1988:70) where readability in the general sense refers to the "ease of understanding due to style of writing" (Klare, 1963:1) as opposed to legibility, which mainly pertains to typographic aspects such as font type, font size, and line spacing.

According to design guidelines by Lent (1980), Zimmermann and Perkin (1982), Colle and Glass (1986), Van Aswegen and Steyn (1987), Boeren (1994), Brouwer (1995) and Hugo (1996), the readability of an instructional illustration is usually heightened by:

- ensuring that the subject matter depicted is as familiar as possible to the target group,
- avoiding excessive image detail that may distract from the main message of the illustration (the use of plain backgrounds is often encouraged),
- depicting the subject matter as realistically as possible or minimizing the difference in appearance between the real-life object as perceived in an everyday viewing situation on the one hand and its pictorial representation on the other hand, and
- avoiding pictorial conventions (e.g. speech bubbles) unless these are familiar to the target group.

Other criteria not covered in any of the above items that form part of the BLIX analysis for image readability by Pettersson (1984, 1993:159) are that:

- the legend of the illustration should be brief, easy to understand and deal with the image
- the illustration should have a dominant center of interest at or near its optical center.

An alternative approach to image readability is the Picture Readability Index (PRI) for instructional illustrations developed by Lantz (1996). Lantz proceeds from the standpoint that the processing of visual information comprises two main phases (see Spoehr and Lehmkuhle, 1982). In the first phase, affective or emotional impressions towards the image are formed as the viewer scans the image with rapid eye fixations. During the first phase, the viewer becomes aware of basic forms, begins to explore the image and starts to speculate about why it was created. The value that the image has for the viewer personally is also determined, which implies that the visual reading process may be terminated directly after the first phase should the viewer experience dislike or indifference towards the image.

The second phase of image processing is more cognitive in nature. During the second phase, the viewer relates the data obtained during first glance responses to existing knowledge structures or schemata and also creates new schemata around new information. In the second phase, the viewer may discover relationships between visual elements that inspire visual interest, determine whether there is a direct relationship between the image and its caption, and decide whether the image accomplishes its objective as defined by the caption.

The procedure followed during PRI testing involves displaying an image for a short duration and then asking the respondent to draw the basic forms perceived, followed by a questionnaire consisting of 77 questions to assess affective perception of the image. Thereafter, the caption of the illustration is provided and the respondent completes a second questionnaire containing 80 questions dealing with cognitive perception of the image and its caption after prolonged exposure to the illustration. Illustrations that stimulate a high degree of visual processing during both phases are considered very readable, designated with a high PRI score. A low PRI score is allocated to illustrations that are associated with low levels of visual processing during the two phases.

Cultural Bias

The Latin roots of the term culture, *cult* (a reverent relationship) and *ur* (earth), suggest a dynamic and evolving relationship between a community and its environment that results in the production of local knowledge (Griggs, 1999:1). Servaes and Lie (1996) regard culture as a phenomenon that differs from community to community,

...generally because the living conditions of these societies differ. Consequently, each culture has to be analyzed on the basis of its own "logical" structure. Each culture operates out of its own logic. (p. 4)

The study of culture has been described as the study of what meanings are available for use in a given society from the wider range of possible meanings and the way in which members of a society choose and use meanings from available meanings (Schudson, 1989:156; Leeds-Hurwitz, 1993:16).

Flowing from the above, cultural bias may be defined as a rigid inclination toward meanings rooted in local knowledge and local logic that may come across either as a deliberate prejudice or as an unintended neglect (O'Sullivan, Hartley, Saunders, Montgomery & Fiske, 1994:29). Two main undesirable scenarios that correspond with the above described visual processing phases by Lantz (1996) unfold when cultural bias plays a major role during the viewing process of an instructional illustration. These are:

- cultural bias prevents the target community from exploring the illustration beyond first glance responses on the literal level of meaning and the viewing process is terminated after a brief affective phase
- if the cognitive phase of image processing is reached, cultural bias in the target community leads to the formation of unintended or aberrant interpretations on the figurative level of meaning.

With regard to the first scenario, cultural bias in the target community is often based on a lack of familiarity with the depicted subject matter. For example, a target group not acquainted with a mythological figure such as Pegasus, the winged horse on which Bellerophon rode against Chimaera (Evans, 1990:835), may easily become frustrated with this aspect of an image and abort the viewing process before reaching the cognitive phase. On a more subtle level, the ethnic group of human models used, the brand names of products (De Lange, 1999), or the type of vegetation and environmental

lighting depicted in an illustration may cause the target community to reject the illustration along the lines of its being different, such as *not what we are used to or not meant for us*.

Concerning the second scenario, cultural bias may lower image readability even though the target community moves from the affective to the cognitive phase of image processing and experiences the illustration as engaging. In this scenario, the target group attaches implied or figurative meanings to the depicted subject matter that significantly alter the overall meaning of the illustration. For example, Van Aswegen and Steyn (1987:76) describe a health education poster about oral health where an image of a pineapple was included in order to illustrate that fresh fruit in a diet promotes oral health. A significant proportion of the rural Swazi-speaking target community attached the connotation "brewing beer" to the pineapple in line with the local custom of using pineapples to brew fruit beer. This could have been avoided had an alternative fruit such as an apple been used to convey the concept. Similarly, Boeren (1994:83) reports on a community in which the superstition is commonly held that if a pregnant woman eats fish her fetus will slip out. It should be self evident that an instructional message which depicts a pregnant woman eating fish in order to illustrate that a healthy diet is recommended during pregnancy is very likely to be misread in that specific target community.

Audience Participation

Mody (1991), among others, has argued that a reliable estimate of the potential cultural bias in a particular target community can be obtained by following an audience-participation-based approach. In the participatory model, the emphasis is on information exchange rather than on persuasion (Servaes, 1995:12), where producers:

... listen and observe first, and then present draft messages (story boards, scripts, photographs) to the community to validate whether they conform to their needs and customs. (Mody, 1991, p. 28)

Mody (1991:53) suggests specific steps that can be taken to achieve audience involvement during the design phase of an illustration to include dialogue with a sample of the target community about image contents and design preferences. However, in a study about the readability of visual rhetoric in a population consisting of 150 literate and 150 non-literate adults in Bloemfontein, South Africa (Gaede, 1999a, 1999b), it soon became clear during the pilot phase that especially non-literate respondents struggled to articulate visual concepts verbally. For example, a question such as, "What photographic technique was used in these three pictures?" proved inappropriate as it required an answer along the lines of, "The camera zooms in on the subject matter when one looks at the images from left to right," which presupposes an understanding of the photographic concept of "zooming in." In contrast, the revised version of the question read, "Does the size of the man's hands get bigger or smaller when one looks at the three images from left to right?" That question could be answered with either "bigger" or "smaller," thus avoiding the potential methodological pitfall that the measurement of visual comprehension is based on advanced verbal articulation.

The above suggests that even though potential cultural bias relating to the choice of subject matter may be identified without much difficulty when an audience participation approach is followed, comprehension of the various ways in which cultural bias may be amplified through the use of formal techniques, such as selective focus or choice of camera position, are more challenging to measure. As the visual literacy literature is rife with concerns that the measurement of manipulation awareness (Messaris, 1994:181) and other aspects of visual literacy (Avgerinou and Ericson, 1999; see also Baca, 1990) is usually based on verbal responses, further research is necessary to explore ways in which meaningful input about design decisions may best be obtained from verbally non-literate and technologically isolated target groups.

Conclusion

Watson and Hill (1993:18) note that the accusation of bias, in general, tends to be predicated on the assumption that there is an opposite or objectivity, and further, that impartiality is not only possible but desirable. With regard to the readability of an instructional illustration, where the aim is to convey visual information as unambiguously as possible, the challenge for the producer thus lies in accommodating the potential lack of objectivity in the target community as far as possible during the design phase.

In the end, learning more about the cultural bias of others can be a very enriching experience. In this regard, I will leave you to think about the words of Bakhtin (1986) who wrote that:

"There exists a very strong, but one-sided and thus untrustworthy, idea that in order to better understand a foreign culture, one must enter into it, forgetting one's own, and view the world through the eyes of this foreign culture. This idea, as I have said, is one-sided. Of course, a certain entry as a living being into a foreign culture, the possibility of seeing the world through its eyes, is a necessary part of the process of understanding it; but if this were the only aspect of this understanding, it would merely be duplication and would not entail anything new or enriching." (p. 6)

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